

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING REFLECTIVE ABILITIES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16999217>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the psychological foundations of developing reflexive abilities of an individual in a digital environment. In the modern educational and information space, where digital technologies are widely used, the formation of human thinking, self-knowledge and skills of conscious control of one's actions is of particular importance. The article examines the content, forms and stages of reflection from a psychological point of view, reveals the features of reflection in a digital environment. Effective methods and psychological conditions for developing reflexive abilities using digital technologies are also analyzed. The results of the study especially emphasize the importance of reflection in the educational process to support personal growth, develop critical thinking and independent decision-making skills using digital tools.*

Keywords: *digital environment, reflection, reflective thinking, psychological factors, metacognitive skills, motivation, emotional safety, interactive communication, digital learning, reflective competence.*

Introduction

In the context of the rapid development of modern information and communication technologies (ICT), the education system is also adapting to these changes and seeks to effectively organize the process of teaching and upbringing in the digital environment. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforms are being carried out to digitalize education, in particular, a state policy is being formed based on the concept of "Digital Education" and the principle of "New Uzbekistan - New Education", within the framework of which a personalized approach, the formation of critical and reflective thinking are becoming priority tasks of the pedagogical process [1-2].

At the same time, the issue of developing the reflexive abilities of students in the digital environment, that is, the skills of analysis, evaluation of their thoughts and actions, as well as the correct derivation of conclusions from them, is becoming increasingly relevant from a psychological point of view. Digital technologies not only change the methods of obtaining knowledge and the thinking activity of pupils and students, but also become an important tool for ensuring their independent thinking, decision-making and self-improvement. Therefore, this article examines the psychological aspects of the formation and development of reflexive abilities in the digital environment, and analyses ways to improve this process.

Literature Review

The formation and development of reflexive abilities in the digital environment is a psychologically and pedagogically complex, but relevant area of scientific research. This article analyzes scientific research, concepts and approaches implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the CIS countries on this issue.

In recent years, developments aimed at developing digital education and developing reflective thinking skills in students have been actively carried out by Uzbek scientists. Thus, A.

Saidov and D. Mamatkulov (2022) [3] revealed the psychological foundations of the formation of reflective thinking in schoolchildren, scientifically substantiating the definition of reflection as the ability of an individual to control their own actions. They emphasize the importance of the teacher's pedagogical reflective approach to the development of reflection.

In addition, I. Turaboev (2020) [4], having analyzed the psychological characteristics of digital learning, identified the possibilities of using ICT for personal development. In particular, he emphasizes the need for psychological adaptation of the digital environment to develop critical and reflective thinking in students.

The principle of "New Uzbekistan - New Education" and the concept of "Digital Education" indicate that state policy pays special attention to the integration of reflective competencies into the educational process. These documents serve as a reliable basis for scientific and methodological work.

In the CIS countries, especially in the Russian Federation, there are in-depth scientific studies in the field of psychology of reflection and digital education. For example, L.M. Mitina (2010) [5] developed a methodology for developing reflexive competence in the educational process. In her opinion, reflexive competence is the ability of an individual to analyze, evaluate and correct their mental activity. She considers this as professional reflection in teachers and as a means of personal development in students.

J. Dewey (1933) is recognized as the founder of the theory of reflective thinking. In his work "How We Think", he deeply analyzed the role of reflective thinking in the educational process, the conditions for its emergence and methods of formation. Dewey's theory still serves as a methodological basis for modern educational psychology.

Analysis of these sources shows that, despite the existence of universal approaches to the development of reflexive abilities, the Republic of Uzbekistan is developing its own approaches that take into account its educational system, national values and digital infrastructure.

Research Methodology and Results

The methodological basis of this study was a combination of modern psychological cognitive, socio-psychological and activity-based approaches. The main goal of the study was to identify the mechanisms for the formation of students' reflexive abilities in a digital environment, to determine the psychological factors that contribute to their development, and to develop scientifically based recommendations.

The study was based on the following methodological principles:

-based on cognitive psychology: reflexive thinking was considered as a person's ability to be aware of their thoughts, analyze them, admit mistakes and draw conclusions from them.

-based on a personality-oriented approach: reflection was studied as a process associated with the student's internal need for self-knowledge and the desire for development.

- within the framework of the activity-based approach: reflection was interpreted as an integrative part of educational activities, that is, a way to deepen knowledge through the assessment of results, their rethinking and self-analysis.

Research methods:

Psychological diagnostics: Testing was conducted on 200 participants - students of higher educational institutions and pupils of comprehensive schools to determine the level of reflection.

Survey and interview: Students' opinions were collected on the possibilities of assessing and analyzing their knowledge using digital tools (online tests, platforms, electronic portfolios).

Experimental approach: An experiment was organized based on tasks that develop reflective abilities using digital educational tools (for example, analyzing problem situations, keeping a self-assessment diary, working with digital mind maps).

The results of the study showed the formation of reflective abilities in the digital environment in the following main areas:

There is a positive relationship between reflection and digital tools. The skills of analyzing and assessing one's own thoughts have significantly improved thanks to electronic journals, blogs and reflective forums.

The levels of reflection in pupils and students differ significantly: in higher education, the skills of self-analysis, argumentation and evaluation of one's thoughts are relatively developed, while in general education institutions these processes are not yet sufficiently formed.

In the digital environment, an important factor in the formation of reflection is the psychological competence of the teacher. He should ask reflective questions, organize tasks that encourage mutual analysis, provide criteria for self-assessment.

The development of reflective thinking is directly related to critical thinking, personal responsibility, conscious decision-making and self-regulation skills.

Psychological analysis has shown that with the correct use of digital educational tools, the reflective abilities of students are activated, but this occurs not only at the technical level, but namely due to psychological conditions, motivation, emotional safety, interactive communication and metacognitive skills.

Since digital technologies are deeply integrated into the educational process, the development of reflective abilities requires a modern approach not only from a didactic, but also from a psychological point of view. Table 1 provides a systematic analysis of the psychological factors that contribute to the activation of reflexive abilities when working with digital educational tools, and their functional significance.

Table 1

Psychological factors influencing the formation of reflective abilities in digital education

Psychological factor	Manifestation in digital technologies	Psychological influence on reflexive abilities
Motivation	Incentives through digital games, tests, rating systems	The student approaches the assessment and analysis of his activities with an internal need
Emotional security	Personal account, closed assessment system, safe communication platforms	Creates a positive psychological background for free expression of thoughts, recognition and analysis of mistakes
Interactive communication	Chatbots, online discussions, video responses, group projects	Develops reflection through comparing one's thoughts with others, thinking and communicating
Metacognitive skills	Electronic portfolios, self-assessment tools (quizzes, forums)	The student plans, controls educational activities and draws conclusions

Psychological conditions	Ergonomic interface, user-friendly platform, harmony of visual means	Facilitates adaptation to the digital environment by enhancing psychological preparation for reflective thinking
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Conclusion

Accelerating the learning and knowledge acquisition process in the digital environment poses the challenge for pupils and students to develop reflective thinking, that is, the ability to self-knowledge, self-assessment and self-correction. The study revealed that reflective abilities are not formed automatically only under the influence of digital technologies. They are effectively developed only in conditions of psychological comfort, positive motivation, metacognitive strategies, emotional safety and an interactive environment.

In addition, educational institutions, when using digital teaching aids, need pedagogical and psychological approaches that support reflective thinking. This contributes not only to personal development, but also to the formation of high-level competencies, such as critical thinking, independent decision-making in problem situations and self-improvement.

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